

The Web GIS as an Auxiliary Management Tool for In-Person Teaching with Technological Mediation in the Amazon Rainforest: The Case of CEMEAM, Amazonas, Brazil.

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Abstract

The Amazon faces significant logistical challenges due to its size and complex geographical features, such as the dense rainforest and vast hydrographic network. In Brazil, Amazonas stands out for its ecological diversity and difficulties of access, requiring innovative solutions for educational development. The Amazonas Education Media Centre (CEMEAM) uses In-Person Teaching with Technological Mediation (IPTTM) to overcome these obstacles, promoting digital inclusion and democratizing access to education. Implemented in 2007 by the Amazonas State Secretary of Education and School Sports (SEDUC-AM), it combines face-to-face classes with satellite videoconferences and other media, reaching more than 25.000 students in an area of 1.571.000 km². To help with spatial management, CEMEAM was presented with a proposal for a Geographic Information System in a web environment (WebGIS) using free software and plugins (QGIS and QGIS Cloud) as well as freely accessible products. The WebGIS enabled a variety of analyses and proved it could contribute to more efficient spatial management, adapted to regional specificities, such as the isolation of localities and the dependence of students on river transportation. Although it is not yet a formalized institutional tool, SIG Web demonstrates the potential of geotechnologies in educational management in the Amazon, serving as an important experiment to support CEMEAM in its needs.

1. Introduction

The Amazon, with its vast expanse covering nine South American countries, presents complex logistical challenges due to its international configuration and unique geographical characteristics. In Brazil, the Legal Amazon includes nine of its states, with Amazonas being one of the most prominent, standing out for its immense territorial area and ecological diversity. The dense rainforest, extensive hydrographic network and limited road transportation infrastructure make moving people and goods a major challenge, especially in isolated areas, which also compromises the effectiveness of public policies and requires innovative solutions to promote social inclusion and sustainable development.

For these reasons, the Amazonas Education Media Center (CEMEAM) has emerged as a strategic solution, using Technology-Mediated Education to overcome the obstacles imposed by the region's geography and infrastructure. Its innovative approach not only mitigates logistical limitations, but also promotes interactivity and digital inclusion, strengthening the educational process in a context of unique challenges. Thus, CEMEAM plays a crucial role in the democratization of education in the Amazon, ensuring that physical barriers do not impede the educational and social development of the Amazonian population.

2. Innovation and Technology for Education in the Amazon: CEMEAM

CEMEAM is an initiative of the Amazonas State Government, through its State Department of Education and School Sports (SEDUC-AM), designed to offer innovative, quality education to public school students, using information and communication

technologies with an emphasis on interactivity. Set up in 2007, the Center combines face-to-face classes with satellite videoconferencing resources and media designed for synchronous and asynchronous classes. CEMEAM classes, produced and taught by specialist teachers in each subject area, are broadcast live to classrooms equipped with technology and mediated by face-to-face teachers. In addition, the Center broadcasts lectures and courses in partnership with other government bodies, in a geographical context peculiar to the Amazon region (CEMEAM, 2024a).

CEMEAM's classes are broadcast via IPTV (Internet Protocol Television), using the internet to reach 60 municipalities in Amazonas. These broadcasts cover 813 locations, including municipal headquarters, towns, communities and indigenous villages, managed regionally by 111 public schools. These schools run 1.932 classes, serving 25.374 students in an area of 1.571.000 km² of the Brazilian and international Amazon. The levels of education range from Elementary School II to High School, including Youth and Adult Education (EJA), in the afternoon and evening shifts (CEMEAM, 2024b).

It should be clarified that the concept of In-Person Teaching with Technological Mediation (IPTTM) refers to a hybrid educational model that combines elements of Distance Learning (DL) with the routine of face-to-face teaching. Unlike conventional distance learning, IPTTM requires the presence of face-to-face teachers and students in the classroom at set times, while teachers, pedagogical advisors and the entire technical support team remain connected from a transmission center (Campos, 2011).

Considering that spatial complexity is one of the main management challenges for technology-mediated classroom teaching in CEMEAM's operational context, we asked whether a Web GIS (Geographic Information System in a web

environment) would be valid as an auxiliary tool for managing the Center's territorial interests. This geotechnological tool offers low-cost access to spatial data and information that can be constantly updated, including in a participatory way, as well as being easily used by people with basic Internet skills. Web GISs are independent of specific platforms and operating systems in order to be consulted or manipulated, and can be accessed by any web browser, simply by accessing the World Wide Web (Horanont et al., 2002, Nelson, 2002, Painho et al., 2001). Our concern took the form of a research problem and the path of the investigation is described in this paper.

3. Methodology

Once the research problem had been defined, we opted for a case study methodological approach, which was appropriate to our concerns, as it allows for a detailed and rich understanding of the phenomenon being studied, as well as being adaptable to different contexts and types of research. Case studies generate results that are often useful for professionals and managers, as they offer insights that are directly applicable to the context studied (Yin, 2001).

The general objective was to implement a Geographic Information System in a web environment (WebGIS) to be used as an auxiliary spatial management tool at CEMEAM. The specific objectives were to select software and other free Geographic Information System tools for the implementation of the CEMEAM WebGIS, to select data and products that are freely accessible and usable for the CEMEAM WebGIS and to evaluate the possibilities of using the WebGIS according to CEMEAM's management needs.

3.1 Free software

The software chosen was QGIS (version LTR 3.34.7-Prizren) and its QGIS Cloud plugin (version 3.9.12).

QGIS is an open-source GIS that has been around since 2002. It is multiplatform (Unix, Windows, and macOS) and has a user-friendly interface that allows you to view, edit and analyze data, compose maps, print them and publish them on the Internet using the WMS (Web Map Service), WCS (Web Coverage Service), WFS (Web Feature Service) and OAPIF (OGC API - Features) protocols using a web server. It has a wide range of plugins for various purposes and offers a version for mobile devices (QGIS.Org, 2024). In addition, the software has extensive documentation on its official website, as well as an active, productive and cooperative community in several countries, which greatly facilitates its use.

The QGIS Cloud plugin allows complex maps to be created, published and managed on the web in just a few minutes, using QGIS Desktop for styling and the QGIS Cloud plugin for publishing. It offers a complete PostgreSQL database with PostGIS spatial extension, making it easy to create and administer databases directly from the plugin, with compatibility for tools such as pgAdmin or QGIS Database Manager. Data and maps can be shared via OGC (Open Geospatial Consortium) compatible web services, such as WMS for viewing and WFS for downloading and editing. In addition, it allows high-quality maps to be printed on a variety of paper sizes and resolutions of up to 1200 dpi, providing total flexibility in the production of print layouts (QGIS Cloud, 2021).

It should be emphasized that in developing this proposal for a Web GIS for CEMEAM, the free version of QGIS Cloud was used for exclusively demonstrative and exploratory purposes. This choice was justified by the need to exemplify the platform's functionalities and potential, especially in a context of limited resources for the initial project phase. It is important to clarify that QGIS Cloud Free is a tool with usage restrictions, including limitations for commercial and governmental purposes. As such, its use in this article serves only to illustrate a possible path for the implementation of a Web GIS, and not for definitive operational purposes.

When considering the adoption of a WebGIS at CEMEAM, it is necessary to evaluate alternative solutions, such as paid versions of QGIS Cloud or other software that allows institutional use in compliance with legislation and free software policies applicable to the public sector. Therefore, this use of QGIS Cloud Free does not imply its final recommendation for effective implementation, but rather a preliminary demonstration of technical feasibility.

3.2 Free products

All the products needed to create the GIS and, consequently, the GIS Web, were selected from sources that freely available. We started with a report on the distribution of the antennas receiving the IPTV signal, which generated a layer of points from the locations of the schools or other institutions responsible for distributing the signal in CEMEAM's Technology-Mediated Education classrooms (CEMEAM, 2024b).

We also collected a layer of points from the locations of the seats of the municipalities in the state of Amazonas and other polygonal layers referring to the state's territorial organization, such as divisions into municipalities, mesoregions, micro-regions and the Metropolitan Region of Manaus (MMA, 2006). In addition to these, we searched for a polygonal layer with grid of point/orbit information from the LandSat WRS-2 satellites (USGS, 2024). Remember that the Worldwide Reference System-2 (WRS-2) refers to the LandSat 4 satellites and above.

3.3 Preparing the Desktop GIS

This stage began with the transformation of the geographical coordinates spreadsheet into a points layer with the locations of the IPTV signal receiving antennas at the various points served by CEMEAM. Next, the CRS (Coordinate Reference System) and EPSG (European Petroleum Survey Group) codes of each of the layers to be included in the GIS were checked for compatibility, with WGS-84 (World Geodetic System 1984) being chosen as the standard datum (EPSG:4326). The following layers were added to the project: location of IPTV antennas and municipal offices (points), areas/boundaries of the municipalities, micro-regions and meso-regions of the state of Amazonas, as well as the Metropolitan Region of Manaus (RMM) and a constant grid of points/orbits from the LandSat WRS-2 satellites (polygons).

After configuring the presentation of each layer, the print layout was created. Although we are aware that different layouts can be added to the Web GIS, to be used via QGIS Cloud, we opted at first for an A4 size template, landscape orientation, where the basic elements of a cartographic representation were added, namely title, orientation, graphic and numerical scale, geographic coordinates and authorship. It is important to emphasize that the numerical scale is added via text, not automated, which forces the

printing relationship with the scale of 1:8000000 (where one unit equals 80 km), to validate the layout.

Figure 1. The Desktop GIS.

3.4 Publishing the WebGIS

At this point, with the QGIS Cloud plugin already installed, we created a user account and logged in. Following simple and intuitive steps, we send the layers to be included in the WebGIS, which are accompanied by the print layout we used for the first version, which does not appear in the list of layers to be sent.

In the final step of the publication, it is possible to add background layers to the map, choosing from several available alternatives, such as Swisstopo, OpenStreetMap, OpenTopoMap, OSM/Thunderforest and Bing Maps. We chose to use the OpenStreetMap and OpenTopoMap layers, the latter in its OSM OpenTopoMap variant, which provides a topographic map combining relief and infrastructure information. After setting up the background layers, simply click on “Publish Map”. In a few seconds, the QGIS Cloud plugin processes the publication and automatically generates the links to access the WebGIS, allowing the map to be viewed and shared with other users in a practical and efficient way.

It's important to remember that QGIS Cloud, in its free version, allows unlimited public maps (for non-commercial/non-governmental use only), as well as a PostGIS 3.1 database (with a total volume of 50 MB and a maximum of 10 simultaneous database connections). In the paid version, the capacity rises to 500 MB, ten PostGIS 3.1 databases, customization of WebGIS using logo and CSS, and other advantages. The paid plan also includes domain name customization, among other features.

4. Results

As a result, the CEMEAM WebGIS was made available on the Internet (Figure 2). For reasons already explained, relating to the license, access was kept restricted. As soon as it was published, we began to evaluate the possibilities for its use, taking into account the specific management needs related to the spatial structure of In-Person Teaching with Technological Mediation (IPTTM).

WebGIS offers the Maps & Tools menu, with submenus Layers & Legends, Map Tools and Print, for configuring the map. In the first menu, you can select the layers Municipal Seats, Localities, Municipalities, Metropolitan Region of Manaus, Microregions, Mesoregions, Municipalities (boundaries), OpenStreetMap and OSM OpenTopoMap. It is also possible to insert WMS, WFS,

WMTS (Web Map Tile Service) layers, among others, via URL (Uniform Resource Locator). In the Map Tools submenu, you can acquire point positions via coordinates, as well as take distance, area and direction measurements. Under Print (Figure 3), there are options for print layout, map scale, resolution in three options (150, 300 and 600 dpi), as well as map rotation and grid settings.

Figure 2. The WebGIS.

The GIS Web interface also has a search field with different options, including information from the OpenStreetMapSearch layer. By clicking on features, you can obtain information from the attribute tables of each layer in the Feature Information window. For example, clicking on municipal boundaries provides information such as the name of the municipality, the Federation Unit code, the mesoregion, the microregion, among others. Clicking on the points referring to the municipal seats provides information on how many locations have IPTV reception antennas, their locations by coordinates, the names of the localities (city, town, community or indigenous village), the names of the schools (headquarters and local), the classes in operation and other relevant data. We must stress the importance of organizing the attribute table for each layer added to the project, since the data establishes the options for querying the Web GIS.

Figure 3. Print layout of the WebGIS.

With regard to the LandSat WRS-2 grid layer, we would like to clarify that this is to facilitate the search for images from those satellites according to point/orbit information, which we do using EarthExplorer (USGS, 2024). The same search can be carried out by the coordinates of the locations of interest, as well as in other ways, in EarthExplorer. This means that we can consult the environmental characteristics shown by the images, especially when we need to check the flood/drought conditions of the rivers, a factor that reflects on the possibility (or not) of waterway

logistics and, consequently, the students' access to the class locations.

5. Conclusions

Given the dynamics demonstrated, it is necessary for the CEMEAM Web GIS to be constantly evolving, with the main objective of providing relevant tools and insights to improve the management of the IPTTM's educational model, especially in the face of the unique challenges posed by the vast distances and physical characteristics of the Amazon. This WebGIS allows for detailed analysis, such as the location of classes, the accessibility of communities to classrooms and IPTV transmission centers, as well as the management of routes and transportation - with an emphasis on river routes, which are fundamental in the region due to the abundance of rivers that serve as the main access routes for many communities.

In addition, WebGIS offers other possibilities, such as monitoring academic performance by region, identifying infrastructure shortages, strengthening community engagement to promote more participatory and inclusive educational management - especially by motivating student attendance - and planning Environmental Education initiatives. These actions are especially relevant in Amazonian contexts, where the natural environment imposes specific challenges, such as the isolation of communities, the lack of basic infrastructure and dependence on river transportation.

For these actions to be effective, it is essential to understand the specific physical characteristics of the locations assisted by the IPTTM, such as the density of the forest, the hydrographic network, the rugged topography and the distances between communities. These variables directly affect educational logistics, access to mediated teaching technologies and the planning of community involvement strategies, especially in times of extreme drought and forest fires that have affected the region over the last two years (2023-2024).

Finally, the purpose of setting up this WebGIS was to introduce spatial analysis tools to CEMEAM and its managers, demonstrating the possibility of implementing it. In this sense, WebGIS is not yet a formalized institutional tool, but it serves as an important experiment to show how geotechnologies can support educational management in a context as challenging as the Amazon.

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